

PROTECTION OF THE GROWING YOUNG GENERATION FROM GLOBAL THREATS IS THE MOST IMPORTANT FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EVERY COUNTRY.

Aliev Maksudjon Anvarovich

Master's student at the Law Enforcement Academy

E-mail: aliyevm1990@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11441515>

Abstract. In this article, the increase of the world's population in the coming years and, at the same time, the issues of eliminating and preventing the influence of global networks on the minds of people, especially on growing minors, occupying them with a certain work in order to use their free time effectively, and thus protecting them from various threats are covered.

Regarding the above-mentioned issues, first of all, by ensuring the employment of minors by classifying the age at which they can work according to the types of work, ending discrimination in labor and illegal employment, and further improving the responsibility established to attract them to work that they cannot work, it is concluded that global threats to them will be prevented.

Key words: population, world, minor, unemployed, global network, child rights, discrimination, illegal employment, responsibility.

Entrance

Today's rapidly developing times require every country to conduct a strong and fair policy in the social and economic spheres.

Because, in terms of demographics, the growth of the world's population is increasing year by year, which means meeting the growing needs through new views of the renewed world, new models, and new innovations, making timely reforms in every field in order to ensure the human rights that are recognized in the international arena, and through this, just and necessary decisions that are beneficial in all aspects.

According to statistics, the world population will be 7.91 billion in 2021, 7.97 billion in 2022, 8.04 billion in 2023, and 8.11 billion as of May 12, 2024, and this figure will reach 8.54 billion by 2030, 9.19 billion in 2040, and 9.71 billion by 2050 [1].

Uzbekistan, which ranks first in terms of population in Central Asia, had a population of 34.5 million in 2021, 35.3 million in 2022, 36.0 million in 2023, and 36.7 million as of April 1, 2024. (The average growth in the last 5 years was 2 percent per year.) This figure will be 41.7 million by 2030, 48.2 million by 2040, and 55.4 million by 2050 [2].

The main part

Through today's global networks, in which public threats affecting people's minds are increasing, it is necessary to carry out far-sighted reforms, especially in this regard, to support and protect the growing young generation in every way, to help them in the way of their wishes and desires, physically. In order for him to mature mentally and spiritually and to become a child loyal to the motherland, it is necessary to implement clear measures so that he can spend every free moment meaningfully, usefully, and wisely.

“Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” was approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, and 100 clearly oriented goals were defined in the implementation of this development strategy.

In the future, a number of tasks regarding the improvement of state policy regarding youth have been mentioned, including ensuring the rights, freedoms, and legal interests of young people, creating conditions for their employment, creating conditions for the development of entrepreneurship, and striving for a healthy lifestyle. formation, as well as the creation of conditions for the meaningful organization of free time and mass development of youth sports, further development of cooperation with international organizations operating in the field of realization of their rights and freedoms, and the implementation of systematic measures related to youth in a number of other areas [3].

Also, the President of our country, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, spoke at the video selector meeting held on April 11, 2023, "On measures to increase the effectiveness of work in the field of youth policy and further improve the system of working with them," and said, "Let all the leaders know one thing: for the owners of our tomorrow, working with young people is a matter of life and death for us! How will we build New Uzbekistan if we do not create conditions for young people today if we do not advance revolutionary initiatives to support them?" they emphasized [4].

At the same time, in the following years, in order to prevent lack of control and carelessness by working with young people in our country, training them and giving them knowledge, preparing them for professions, engaging them in professions that suit their interests and desires, and organizing their free time in a meaningful way, special tasks have been assigned to all government agencies, starting from the neighborhood seven. This has been determined, and today significant work is being done in this regard.

However, in the current dangerous time of global network activation, it is necessary to direct the growing youth to a specific profession from a young age

to prevent them from being unsupervised and neglected at every moment by further reforming the existing procedures related to their employment and to eliminate the unproductive use of their free time and addiction to social networks. And in order to achieve high efficiency in this regard, it is important to further improve the norms of some national legal documents regarding the labor of minors, as well as to introduce them into practice by integrating the experience of foreign countries into the national legislation.

Sh.A. Ismoilov, A.A. Inoyatov, N.M. Teshaev, M.M. Makhamatov, and economist Z.R. Khudaiberdiev, among the legal scholars of our country, as part of their scientific research on the labor rights of special categories of persons, including minors A number of related scientific studies have been studied [5].

Also, in scientific articles published by legal scholars B.M. Hamrokulov, M.A. Usmanova, M.K. Shomirzaev, and A.B. Khayitov, opinions and comments were expressed about the importance of minors' labor [6].

In this context, the following factors related to the labor of minors are relevant today:

- that minors cannot fully use their labor rights;
- Youth unemployment remains high;
- the occurrence of illegal employment;
- increase in delinquency among young people;
- that discrimination in the employment of minors is not being eliminated;
- that the existing types of work are not completely differentiated

according to the age of a person.

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that today's social network is empty in order to ensure the employment of minors in increasingly dangerous times, to eliminate discrimination in labor and illegal employment, to further improve the responsibility for attracting them to work that they cannot work, and to prevent them from being left unsupervised and neglected. Organizing the effective use of time and thereby guaranteeing a comfortable life is the most important factor in the development of every country.

List of references:

1. <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population>.
2. Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, open data, <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika>.
3. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.GROW?locations=UZ>
4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated 28.01.2022, Lex.uz database, Tashkent-2022.

5. From the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Measures to increase the effectiveness of work in the field of youth policy" held on 11.04.2023 at the meeting of the video selector.
6. Sh.A. Ismoilov- Features of legal regulation of labor of certain categories of employees, doctoral dissertation, Tashkent-2020, A.A. Inoyatov- Labor law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Textbook for higher educational institutions.-T: Economics and Law World Publishing House 2002, M.M. Makhamatov - International legal foundations of cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the International Labor Organization, doctoral dissertation, Tashkent- 2019, N.M. Teshayev - Uzbekistan Principles of legal regulation of labor relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan-Textbook, Tashkent 2019, Z.R.Khudayberdiev-Improving the mechanism of the labor market in the conditions of the formation of an innovative economy, doctoral dissertation, Tashkent-2020, B.M.Khamrokulov-Aktualnyeproblemysotsialno-humanitarnykh nauk, electronic journal, International legal protection of minors, Tashkent-2023, p. 136-137, M.A. Usmanova- Evraziskiy jurnal prava, finansov i prikladnyx nauk, The role of the right to work in the system of human rights, 2023, p. 198, M.Kh.Shomirzaev-Obrazovanie i innovatsionnye issledovaniya zurnal SP-1, The principle of historicity in the interdisciplinary introduction of students to the spectral-variant components of national crafts in school technology education, 2021, A.B. Khayitov- A.B. Khayitov- S.R. Nair The link between women entrepreneurship, innovation and stakeholder engagement: Journal of Business Research, Increasing population employment: Theory and practice, 2022 y 182-p.

